

The Ground of Social Hope In Richard Rorty's Ungroundable Philosophy

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Abstract

This paper explores Richard Rorty's (1931-2007) emphasis on social hope within his broader pragmatist frame of thought, questioning his claim that hope lacks justification. By examining the roles of anti-Platonism, solidarity, and human agency – concepts that occupy a central position in Rorty's thought – I aim to demonstrate that his own version of pragmatism provides a distinctive ground for social hope of a global egalitarian utopia. Rorty's rejection of Platonic metaphysics, which depends on transcendent truths and ultimate grounds, leads him to stress the contingency of human history, the creative potential of language, and the transformative capacity of individuals and communities. Within this anti-foundational vision, hope is detached from metaphysical assumptions yet remains vital as a moral and political orientation. While Rorty insists that hope cannot be justified in any foundational or universal sense, he does not reduce it to an irrational sentiment or attitude. On the contrary his philosophy endorses the rationality of the liberal hopes. Therefore, I argue that his focus on the unjustifiability of hope should be read as a critique of the false hopes offered by traditional metaphysics. This critique leads Rorty toward a liberal and solidaristic form of social hope within historical contingency. The human subject's pursuit of happiness gives rise to a conception of hope that is non-universal yet carries a universal potential. Rorty's pragmatist philosophy thus enables a form of hope that is both self-conscious and responsible – rooted not in metaphysical assurances but in human creativity.

Keywords: Pragmatism, Social Hope, Anti-Platonism, Liberal Democracy, Happiness.

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Richard Rorty'nin Temellendirme Karşıtı Düşüncesinde Toplumsal Umudun Temeli

Öz

Bu makalede, Richard Rorty'nin (1931-2007) pragmatist düşünce çerçevesi içinde toplumsal umuda verdiği önem ele alınmakta ve umudun gerekçelendirilemez olduğu yönündeki iddiası sorgulanmaktadır. Çalışmanın amacı; Rorty düşüncesinde merkezi bir yer tutan anti-Platonizm, dayanışma ve insan öznesinin rolleri çerçevesinde, Rorty'ci pragmatist yaklaşımın küresel eşitlikçi bir ütopya umudu için özgün bir temel sunduğunun gösterilmesidir. Rorty, aşkın doğrulara ve nihai temellere dayanan Platonik metafiziği reddederek, insanlık tarihinin olumsuzluğunu, dilin yaratıcı potansiyelini ve bireyler ile toplulukların dönüştürücü kapasitesini vurgular. Bu temellendirme karşıtı olan bakış açısı kapsamında, umut metafizik varsayımlardan bağımsız hale gelir, ancak ahlaki ve politik bir yönelim olarak hayati önem taşımaya devam eder. Rorty, umudun herhangi bir temellendirici ya da evrensel zeminde gerekçelendirilemeyeceğini iddia etse de, onu irrasyonel bir tutuma ya da duyguya da indirgemez. Aksine, Rorty'nin felsefesi liberal umutların rasyonelliğine arka çıkar. Bu nedenle, Rorty'nin umudun gerekçelendirilemezliğine yaptığı vurgunun, geleneksel metafiziğin sunduğu sahte umutlara yöneltilmiş bir eleştiri olarak okunması gerektiğini ileri sürmekteyim. Nitekim tam da bu eleştiri Rorty'yi tarihsel olumsuzluk içindeki liberal ve dayanışmacı bir toplumsal umuda yöneltir. İnsan öznesinin mutluluğu hedefleyişi evrenselci olmayan ama evrensel potansiyel taşıyan bir umut anlayışı geliştirir. Böylece Rorty'nin pragmatist felsefesi, metafizik güvencelere değil, insanın yaratıcılığına dayanan, hem özbilinçli hem de sorumlu bir umut biçimini mümkün kılar.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Pragmatizm, Toplumsal Umut, Anti-Platonizm, Liberal Demokrasi, Mutluluk.

Introduction

Pragmatism asserts that there is no truth out there to discover. Instead, human beings construct it without any absolute criteria, foundation or guarantee. The world is malleable and waits to be shaped by human action in the absence of any predetermined nature, essential ground, or moral obligation. This anti-realist picture of the world goes hand in hand with hope for social progress (Koopman, 2006, pp. 106-107). Richard Rorty, one of the contemporary pragmatist philosophers, calls for *hope in place of knowledge*, where hope stands for "social hopes... for a global, cosmopolitan, democratic, egalitarian, classless, casteless society" (Rorty, 1999, pp. xii-xiii).² But how can one sincerely maintain hope for a better future in a world open to any possibility? Without any guidance, how can one sustain hope for social progress?

These questions are natural as we often justify our hopes based on our beliefs in the likelihood of desired outcomes. The more likely it is that what is desired will come true, the more hope there is. Indeed, this epistemic process is recognized by the standard philosophical account of hope. Rorty, however, although not giving us an explicit account of hope, does use the

² Rorty seems to equate his notion of hope for a better future with his ideas of liberalism. He uses these expressions interchangeably when he talks about hope: liberal hope, hope for social justice, social hope, public hope, and future hope. For my present purposes, I will not consider whether or not Rorty's descriptions are compatible with the political theory of liberalism. I will therefore use them interchangeably throughout the paper, just as he does.

expression *unjustifiable hope* in some of his dispersed references.³ He emphasizes that “[h]ope does not require justification, cognitive status, foundations, or anything else” (Rorty *et al.*, 2002, p. 58).

This expression of hope evokes some sort of danger. If my hope for something remains the same, in spite of the unfavorable new circumstances, it raises questions about its appropriateness as it could cast doubt on my actions’ rationality. But Rorty’s emphasis seems not to allow such an interpretation once non-essentialist elements in his philosophy are considered. I believe that a closer inspection immediately reveals that the “unjustifiability of hope” in Rorty’s lexicon reflects his rejection of an ultimate ground for any philosophical reasoning.

If so, we can assume that his philosophy offers its own reasons for embracing social hope. Accordingly, in this paper, I argue that his reference to hope is not abstract or unreasonable but is bolstered by a strict rationale in line with his pragmatist ideas. To understand his emphasis on the unjustifiability of hope better, I will begin by referring to his anti-Platonism. Subsequently, I will inquire into the main tenets of his philosophy to identify rational but non-essentialist grounds for his pragmatist liberal hopes. By doing so, I aim to demonstrate that social hope in Rorty’s philosophy is not mere wishful thinking but genuinely depends on his pragmatist conceptualizations of the world.⁴

1. Hope, (Un)Justifiability and Anti-Platonism

Referring to Dewey, Rorty describes the sort of hope that pragmatism embraces: “the ability to believe that the future will be unspecifiably different from, and unspecifiably freer than, the past.” (Rorty, 1999, p. 120) He often talks about “dreaming a better world” (Rorty *et al.*, 2002, p. 58), praises human “imagination” for a superior future, or refers to the faith, love, and hope in the reconstitution ability of human agents as “romance” (Rorty, 1999, pp. 52, 160). On the other hand, he does not completely distance himself from a rational perspective, as one can see in these statements:

I am dubious about using the word “hope” in [the sense of holding a promise beyond reason and planning.] As a pragmatist, I think that what is beyond planning is not worth making promises about. Every promise worth considering has to make a difference to our plans about what to do. (Rorty, 2002, p. 149)

Then, how can we understand his conception of hope? The standard philosophical account, which has various versions and traces back to Hobbes, recognizes two basic elements in hope: (1) a particular desire and (2) the belief in the probability that the desired object would come true.

³ For instance, he states the following when comparing Dewey and Foucault in one of his writings: “Dewey seems to me to have done it better, simply because his vocabulary allows room for unjustifiable hope, and an ungroundable but vital sense of human solidarity.” (Rorty, 1982, p. 208)

⁴ One might object to my project by propounding that Rorty views hope as an epistemic attitude bolstered by historical narratives rather than a matter of philosophical reflection. It is true that a number of passages in Rorty allow this inference. He mentions, for instance, the philosophies of Hobbes, Locke, Marx, Dewey and Rawls as having formed their reasonable future hopes by considering the most recent histories of their own societies (Rorty, 1999, pp. 231-232). Again, he expresses his disbelief that philosophy influences public hope: “I think of the causal influence as going the other way: philosophy is responsive to changes in amount of political hope, rather than conversely.” (Rorty, 1999, p. 229) Still, he does not exclude hope in his philosophy but underlines his reservations: “If one knows what one wants and has some hope of getting it, philosophy can be useful in formulating redescrptions of social phenomena. The appropriation of these redescrptions, and of the jargon in which they are formulated, may speed up the pace of social change.” (1999, p. 232) And elsewhere, while turning to his philosophical elaborations, he says: “Although I think that historical narrative and utopian speculation are the best sort of background for political deliberation, I have no special expertise at constructing such narratives and speculations.” (Rorty, 1999, p. 234) In light of these reservations, I choose to listen to his philosophical reflection and *hope* to get adequately what it conveys.

Thus, the target outcome is possible but not certain when one is affectively living in hope (Meirav, 2009, pp. 217-218; Milona, 2018, pp. 1-2).

Therefore, the justification or rationality of hope can be assessed by these two axes. On the one hand, the desired object should be something good for the hoper in the sense that it is to her benefit. On the other hand, the cognitive component is rational insofar as the target outcome is truly probable (Stahl, 2020, p. 268). For example, hoping to recover from a common illness would be a justified hope, while hoping to recover from an incurable illness would be unjustified.⁵

In Rorty's case, his social hope evidently encompasses the desire for a better future for human beings, characterized by the belief that "unnecessary human suffering can be decreased, and human happiness thereby increased." (Rorty, 2002, p. 154) But what about the belief in the probability of this desired outcome? Is it a deluded belief or not?

At first glance, Rorty's understanding of hope seems to resist this kind of analysis, as he focuses on the unjustifiable hope. It is quite natural to understand this expression as something that "simply is not amenable to rational justification." That is, one cannot argue for or against it, as it remains indifferent to any supporting or destructive reasons (Smith, 2005, pp. 92-93).⁶ But what does this signify in Rorty's vocabulary?

His philosophical outlook primarily reflects an antagonism towards Platonism. He calls the traditional way of doing philosophy as Platonism, which "refers to a set of philosophical distinctions (appearance-reality, matter-mind, made-found, sensible-intellectual, etc.)." For him, Western philosophy has been shaped by these distinctions, which, in fact, pose a threat to social hopes and the sense of human cooperation. As Dewey suggests, this dualistic philosophy, which is ultimately bound to produce metaphysics, is simply the result of the inegalitarian societies of the past. The quest for metaphysical knowledge has failed to deliver on its promises and has instead served the privileged classes within societies (Rorty, 1999, pp. xii, xv, 29). Following Dewey, then, Rorty aims to avoid the unjust consequences of adopted hopes rooted in traditional philosophy.

The main mistake of this tradition lies in the claim of ultimate knowledge for Rorty: From Plato to Marx, philosophers asserted to grasp some universal and unchangeable principles and grounded their explanations to them, like the human soul, nature, inevitable progress of history, language, divine will, god, etc. All these concepts are deemed superior guarantees of attaining the truth. However, time has only revealed their failure (Rorty, 1998, pp. 229-232). Consequently, seeking essentialist or foundationalist explanations in philosophy is itself hopeless (Rorty, 1999, p. 49). In other words, these misleading philosophical endeavors are pragmatically unfruitful to engage in any longer (Malachowski, 2002, p. 38).

Rorty, denying such metaphysical distinctions or claims, *postulates* hope in place of inquiry for ultimate knowledge. He does not seek to justify his hope but rather regards it as the basis of his liberal theory (Stahl, 2020, p. 266). His use of the term unjustifiability, then, can be understood as a part of his central objection to essentialist explanations in philosophy (Smith, 2005, p. 95). His hope lacks an ultimate grounding, but there is nothing wrong with it, as previous reinforcements in this

⁵ The standard account has been criticized for a number of its shortcomings. For some examples and suggestions to meet the challenges, see Meirav, 2009; Smith, 2010, pp. 9-13; Milona, 2018 and Martin, 2014. It is acknowledged that there are various types of hope which are not subject to such a rational explanation. Estimations of probability or calculations of evidence are irrelevant for some kinds, such as religious hope: In this kind, real hope or the essence of hope reveals itself when things seem totally hopeless. In other words, the less empirical or physical probability an anticipated outcome has, the more hope one has for it (Smith, 2005, p. 93). That is why this kind of hope is sometimes called *hope against hope*. See Martin, 2014, pp. 11-34.

⁶ Smith (2005, pp. 92-95) further claims that Rorty's writings contain a more radical sense of unjustifiability, which *resists* any rational analysis due to its romantic elements, and he highlights the tension between these two senses.

way have only led to false expectations. That is why “there is no inferential connection between the disappearance of the transcendental subject – of ‘man’ as something having a nature which society can repress or understand – and the disappearance of human solidarity” (Rorty, 1982, pp. 206-207).

If the term unjustifiability reflects Rorty’s anti-foundationalist philosophy, then, his hope, first, can be regarded rational in a kind of negativity as it suggests achieving better outcomes by relinquishing previous ineffective pursuits. Stated otherwise, it is rationally and pragmatically preferable to embrace hope for a better future rather than persisting in traditional philosophy. Secondly, there is no reason not to assume that Rorty’s philosophy offers its own positive justifications for being hopeful, as Smith offers (Smith, 2005, p. 95). In the rest of the paper, I will delve into his philosophy in detail and try to uncover his peculiar reasons for describing and upholding social and liberal hopes.

2. Cooperation Instead of Knowledge

Pragmatism presents a different understanding of human beings than traditional Greek philosophy. For the latter, we are distinguished from animals with our ability to *know* the reality beyond mere appearances. However, pragmatism follows Darwinism and assumes that human beings are not gifted beings but rather animals with complex behaviors (Rorty, 1999, p. 72). In the absence of any intrinsic nature that defines our lives, Rorty argues for the contingency of self, language, and community (Rorty, 1989). Yet, he gives a distinctive role to the last one:

Plato and Aristotle were wrong in thinking that humankind’s most distinctive and praiseworthy capacity is to know things as they really are. ... My candidate for the most distinctive and praiseworthy human capacity is our ability to trust and to cooperate with other people, and in particular to work together so as to improve the future. (Rorty, 1999, p. xiii)

Certainly, numerous subspecies of animals exhibit the ability to coexist. Many of them even rely on group living as a necessity for their survival. Then, what are the distinctive elements of sociability in human existence? How does Rorty understand this capacity and its role for shaping more promising future? To address these questions, I will begin with his ideas of constructing beliefs and morality.

Now, pragmatism does not maintain that our beliefs correspond to independent realities, be those transcendental or empirical. Instead, Rorty states, drawing upon Davidson, that the world causes us to hold beliefs by which we can sustain our lives. In other words, we adapt ourselves to the environment’s causal pressures imposed on us. Thus, our beliefs become reliable guides for us to pursue our objects (Rorty, 1999, p. 33). Language plays a crucial role in this process, as we express our beliefs in sentences in order to engage in meaningful exchanges with one another (Rorty, 1982, pp. 18-19). In short, our cognitive and linguistic abilities are oriented towards describing things in accordance with our practical needs.

Drawing upon the ideas of Dewey and Davidson, Rorty argues that in such a picture, our beliefs and statements naturally seek justification for survival rather than a special sense of truth pursued by traditional philosophy. This pursuit only ends up escaping from the outside world and a natural frustration, as our beliefs cannot go beyond the human environment, and we can never recognize what we reach at the end of inquiry of truth (Rorty, 1999, pp. 32-34, 82).⁷ Having no high

⁷ Rorty humbly expresses his understanding of truth: “There would only be a higher aim of inquiry called truth if there were such a thing as ultimate justification – justification before God, or before the tribunal of reason, as opposed to any merely finite human audience.” (Rorty, 1999, p. 38)

authority or an ultimate standard to measure our beliefs and statements, our only recourse is to have better justifications in accordance with our goals.

In the absence of ultimate assurances, then, our primary means of justification lies in the realm of intersubjective agreements with fellow human beings. Indeed, as members of a community, we generate efficient justifications for most of our beliefs that meet the community's demands. Because this process has a holistic character, that is, new beliefs have necessary connections with the former ones, we associate newcomers with already justified ones. Thus, what we believe in a society naturally creates a secure web in which we endure our lives (Rorty, 1999, pp. 36-38, 50-51).

That is why for Rorty, morality is just another adjustment and justification process that we have developed over the course of our interactions with other people, rather than a categorically distinct ability of human beings (like Kant's practical reason acting in accordance with an unconditional moral law). Due to our intricate relations in high numbers, we continually redefine our understanding of good and bad behavior and recreate ourselves. Stated otherwise, morality occurs as the culmination of our process of adjustment to each other by shaping our selfhood (Rorty, 1999, pp. 72, 81, 83).

Then, depending on the historical and, thus, impermanent adjustment and consensus of people, the boundaries of the moral community may end at different levels, such as national, gender, racial, etc. What is more, we can never know whether we pursue the ultimate right course of action, just as we can never know what the ultimate truth is. There is no higher power (such as inner self, nature, essence, god, or tribunal), to dictate what we should do. Consequently, future generations, who would be more informed and sophisticated, may judge what we currently consider moral action or true belief (Rorty, 1999, p. 81).

Having said that, Rorty values the West's inclusive political vocabularies as a considerable moral achievement. He believes that these societies happened to develop liberal democratic policies due to mere historical contingencies. As the vocabularies of these societies gradually disconnected from theological and metaphysical presuppositions, human solidarity, defined as "the ability to think of people wildly different from ourselves as included in the range of 'us,'" emerged as moral achievement. This moral progress is certainly not the outcome of a ready-made formula somewhere in human essence. Instead, it is a product of human creation (Rorty, 1989, p. 192). But how?

When it comes to the larger scope of cooperation as in the case of solidarity, Rorty is not content with the explanation of adjusting to others. While he provides intersubjectivity to test our beliefs, he now turns to an ability of us that we experience individually: our sensitivity to pain, and humiliation - a special form of pain peculiar to human beings (Rorty, 1989, p. 177). As we become aware of others' suffering, we begin to respond to more people's interests and needs than we previously did. If so, moral progress is possible not by searching for ultimate moral codes but rather by improving our capacity to identify human pain and enlarge our moral community (Rorty, 1999, pp. 81-82). These seem to be the first keys to believing in a better future in Rorty's descriptions.

3. Shared Ability to Suffer Humiliation and to Notice it

Suffering humiliation and noticing others' suffering make any other difference (like language, habits, and countries) unimportant among human beings (Rorty, 1989, p. 192). But what do they actually mean? Why do they play such a big role in social hope and solidarity?

Firstly, humiliation differs from physical pain, which all animals typically experience. Instead, it conveys "mental, symbolic or emotional pain," which Rorty mostly uses as a synonym

for cruelty (Erez, 2011, p. 29). It causes people long-lasting pain since it transforms anything significant in one's life that makes one unique into something "futile, obsolete, and powerless" (Rorty, 1989, p. 89). The examples he gives are as follows:

Consider what happens when a child's precious possessions – the little things around which he weaves fantasies that make him a little different from all other children – are redescribed as "trash," and thrown away. Or consider what happens when these possessions are made to look ridiculous alongside the possessions of another, richer, child. ... The same sort of thing sometimes happens to nonintellectuals in the presence of intellectuals. (Rorty, 1989, pp. 89-90)

This passage suggests that the target of humiliation is selfhood. It emerges while constructing holistic beliefs and morality in a given language and environment. We describe ourselves and tell ourselves coherent stories in this way (Rorty, 1989, pp. 177-178). Likewise, a child's possession of toys is a fundamental part of his/her world and story. Humiliation, then, is so destructive in life in the sense of annihilating this coherent story. As Erez argues, the centrality of humiliation arises from its power to render any activity of an individual meaningless (Erez, 2011, pp. 29-31).⁸

Another aspect of humiliation is that it can occur unintentionally as well as on purpose. In fact, Rorty's examples tell us that the offender does not have to be aware of the situation. The poorer child's feelings in the presence of a rich child, or nonintellectual's in the environment of intellectuals, are not always the result of deliberate actions. It might follow from mere negligence (Erez, 2011, p. 31). This indicates that humiliation has a vast scope to render us powerless, independent of any explicit or obvious threat. That is why the second ability of human being has a significant effect on moral progress: noticing humiliation.

Given that Rorty attributes a sense of responsibility to the type of intellectual whom he calls liberal ironist on this matter, it might be worthwhile to portray her briefly. Now, Rorty calls the set of words by which we justify our beliefs and actions or pursue our hopes as final vocabulary. It is final because we cannot argue for its worth in a noncircular way as we do not have a meta-vocabulary to test our own. The ironist is the one who is skeptical about her own final vocabulary, as she is well aware of alternatives of others (people from other communities) as a result of her extensive readings or in-person interactions. She realizes that none of them is any closer to an ultimate reality as each one is developed contingently. Because each is equally fragile and rootless, "anything can be made to look good or bad by being redescribed." In short, the one who recognizes that her final language, society, and constructed self cannot be justified by any foundation and that things might have been otherwise is an ironist (Rorty, 1989, pp. 73-75).

The ironist is recommended to continue her acquaintance with other vocabularies by which she can recreate herself in order to address these doubts. He says, "[w]e ironists hope, by this continual redescription, to make the best selves for ourselves that we can." Without any selection criteria, the ironist's doubts can only be eliminated by expanding her repertoire of other vocabularies, cultures, and selves. Rorty sees reading as the easiest way to meet different people from all over the world. Novels, poems, plays, and literary critics in particular are moral guidance for an ironist because they provide a rich source for the various webs of beliefs (Rorty, 1989, pp. 80-81).

⁸ Rorty discusses a severe version of humiliation in his reading of George Orwell's *1984*. Here, he interprets Winston Smith's torture for changing his present beliefs as breaking his self because newcomers will not allow him to keep his coherent web of beliefs. Realizing this incoherency is where the crack starts. The ultimate humiliation occurs when the whole story about oneself is torn down (Rorty, 1989, pp. 178-179), and thereby one loses the meaning he/she has given to her/his life. Therefore, humiliation has the power to demolish the personality that has been built up until then.

Then, very naturally, irony becomes a private matter. Because an ironist experiences a permanent contrast between the final vocabulary she inherits and the ones she wants to recreate, she would be alienated from her own society (Rorty, 1989, pp. 87-88). Furthermore, her beliefs are never backed up by essential reference points. But this does not imply that an ironist cannot commit to liberal social hopes. On the contrary, she maintains her hope together with her ungroundable desires. There is still room to expect that human suffering will be reduced and people will no longer humiliate one another (Rorty, 1989, p. xv). How so?

For Rorty, encountering alternative lives is not just for liberal ironist's her own edification. This also enables her to notice "the actual and possible humiliation of the people who use these alternative final vocabularies" (Rorty, 1989, p. 92). She could easily detect suffering thanks to his imaginative skills developed by his recursive acquaintance with other stories. As she can transcend her own final vocabulary, she is able to redescribe herself and unfamiliar ones, hence, turn *them* into *one of us*. As a result, she is able to urge people to adopt and use new vocabularies (Rorty, 1989, pp. xvi, 78, 93).

This role of ironist is crucial because victims of cruelty cannot express themselves in their vocabulary. In essence, there is no such thing as the language of the victims or the voice of the oppressed because victims become perplexed. Their vocabulary is destroyed and has yet to be replaced with a new one. For this reason it is the responsibility of others, such as novelists, poets, journalists, or ethnographers, to make their suffering audible. But the task of recognizing the cases is of the ironist. She is able to identify what most people miss and alert others to the silent forms of humiliation (Rorty, 1989, pp. 93-94).

4. Why and How Not Be Cruel?

Rorty insists that the possibility of suffering humiliation is nothing more than a "shared ability" of our species. However, recognizing humiliation is an ability and desire that has shown up primarily in Europe and America lately (Rorty, 1989, pp. 91-93). It would not be wrong to say that human beings have developed these skills through the process of biological and cultural evolution which astonishes us (Rorty, 1999, p. 28). They should be the outcome of human beings' complex cognitive and linguistic capabilities.

But why should moral progress require us to avoid humiliation? Why not be cruel if respecting the selfhood of others does not bring us any closer to the true nature of humanity? Rorty believes that these questions are of only a metaphysician or theologian who wants to argue for his negative attitude to cruelty with something essential or foundational but not of a liberal ironist (Rorty, 1989, pp. xv, 91).

A liberal ironist does not need to justify her actions against cruelty with something superior like nature, god, history, etc. Only circular arguments can prove the liberal claim that "cruelty is the worst thing we do."⁹ (Rorty, 1989, p. 197) She, therefore, starts acting morally by asking directly, "what humiliates?" For her, a moral subject is "something that can be humiliated" by definition. One's capacity to suffer humiliation is sufficient for others to respect his/her selfhood (Rorty, 1989, p. 91).

Then, Rorty's greater sense of solidarity or future hope is said to be developed against a common danger. It is a sort of danger because, as was already stated, we naturally do not want to see our consistent world of beliefs and stories destroyed. He calls this shared desire among us *selfish hope* (Rorty, 1989, pp. 91-92), which reminds us of the self-preservation principle of the organic wholes.

⁹ The statement was made by Judith Shklar and embraced by Rorty in his treatment and defense of liberalism.

If so, the obvious question arises: How would people redescribe their world with the help of ironist, if they naturally resist being redescribed and want to count on their own terms to prevent their world from being demolished? How would they alter their final vocabulary for social progress? Rorty, being aware of this problem, proposes the idea that redescrptions can be made separately for public and private purposes. In private, one may redescribe everything, which may include the humiliation of others.¹⁰ But none of these have bearing on public actions. Everyone agrees to pursue liberal principles against cruelty in public life (Rorty, 1989, pp. 91-92).

Rorty defends this distinction, which has been subject to a great deal of criticisms,¹¹ by saying that private self-creation and human solidarity are equally valid yet “forever incommensurable” (Rorty, 1989, p. xv). He states that “[f]or public purposes, it does not matter if everybody’s final vocabulary is different, as long as there is enough ... overlapping words – words like ‘kindness’ or ‘decency’ or ‘dignity’” (Rorty, 1989, pp. 92-93).

If the picture Rorty draws is on these overlapping words in circulation, then the liberal free society should be the very condition for his prospect of greater human solidarity. The moral responsibility of the ironist can work only in such a community composed of a minimal sense of sensitivity to humiliation. Only in this society would the ironist not deny her fellows’ whole vocabulary. Stated otherwise, ironist and non-ironist share a common ground made up of liberal principles in this interaction. Thereby, the former can maintain her public task while the latter is open to redescription without himself falling into humiliation.

On the other hand, the liberal common ground holds a significance that extends beyond the moral responsibility for the ironist, as it is also something essential for her to be able to breathe:

[H]istorical facts ... suggest that without the protection of something like the institutions of bourgeois liberal society, people will be less able to work out their private salvations, create their private self-images, reweave their webs of belief and desire in the light of whatever new people and books they happen to encounter. (Rorty, 1989, pp. 84-85)

That is, the possibilities of liberal democracies allow more access to a variety of final vocabularies which promotes self-creation and redescrptions. Thus, both the ironist and the non-ironist can meet at the same minimal sense of selfish hope in these liberal societies. That is why Rorty calls not to “look back behind the processes of socialization” and “start from where *we* are,” where “*we*” denotes twentieth-century liberals but not humanity or all rational beings (Rorty, 1989, p. 198).

Therefore, he speaks on behalf of the “heirs to the historical contingencies which have created more and more cosmopolitan, more and more democratic political institutions” (Rorty, 1989, p. 196) by praising the utopian social hope of the 19th century Europe due to being still the noblest accomplishment in the history (Rorty, 1999, p. 277). He thinks that “it just happened that the rule in Europe passed into the hands of people who pitied the humiliated and dreamed of human equality” (Rorty, 1989, p. 184). Modern Western societies now have all the necessary institutions required for their own progress and future hopes (Rorty, 1989, p. 63).

In short, Rorty’s projection for a better future through a greater sense of solidarity seems to build on the opportunities of the present liberal societies of the West. It is true that he is against

¹⁰ He indeed attributes to the private discourse a vast and independent sense: “For my private purposes, I may redescribe you and everybody else in terms which have nothing to do with my attitude toward your actual or possible suffering. My private purposes, and the part of my final vocabulary which is not relevant to my public actions, are none of your business.” (Rorty, 1989, p. 91)

¹¹ For some examples, see Erez, 2011, pp. 44, n.99.

essentialist or ahistorical claims about humanity and emphasizes the contingency of human history. Yet, he does not refrain from considering liberal cultures the last word in our vocabulary (Rorty, 1989, p. 63). In light of this, his ideal picture of an egalitarian society, can be developed onto these accidental achievements.

5. A Global Liberal Utopia: An Egalitarian World Government

But this is not the end of the story for Rorty. His projection of liberal hope includes everybody, not a small part of the world. He says: “[T]he hope that life will eventually be freer, less cruel, more leisured, richer in goods and experiences, not just for our descendants but for everybody’s descendants” (Rorty, 1989, p. 86). Hope, then, can be expressed as extending the solidarity of prosperous countries across the globe. But is there any rational ground to believe in such a global egalitarian utopia?

Rorty repeatedly expresses that there is little chance that his utopia will come true. He says, “There are nine chances out of ten that things will go to hell.” (Rorty, 1994, p. 112) Elsewhere, he counts reasons not only for the improbability of a global liberal utopia but also for the disappearance of liberalism or democratic freedoms in a hundred years (Rorty, 1999, pp. 273-274).¹² Then, why these “short odds are no reason to stop constructing utopias” (Rorty, 1998, pp. 201, n.26) against the danger of embracing futile hopes in particular?

His views on the extension of Western solidarity to the rest of the world are not articulated. I believe, however, that his writings still provide his pragmatist reasons to maintain hope for such a utopia. In his own words, “what is important is the hope that they [things] might not end badly, because they are not fated to go one way or the other. There is not just one Hegelian story of progress, or one Heideggerian story of nihilism to be told” (Rorty, 1994, p. 112). The fact that there is neither guarantee nor necessity but only contingency is not bad thing at all. From the other side of the issue, we have no fundamental reason to despair. As it once appeared in the Western experience, why not hope for its endurance and even expansion across the universe over time?

Furthermore, Rorty’s emphasis of contingency highlights his understanding of the human being as an agent (Bernstein, 2003, p. 134). “There is nothing deep down inside us except what we have put there ourselves” (Rorty, 1982, p. xiii). Because there is no pre-written destiny of history or any transcendent or foundational guide, the utopias can only come true in the hands of human beings. Since we talk about the human environment, human intersubjectivity and institutions, it is within the human prerogative to bring about the realization of his/her goals, which ultimately points out a power.

Still, why keep hoping that this agency would choose to move towards a sort of egalitarian organizational structure? I believe that Rorty’s final answer would be found in his reference to happiness. As previously stated, pragmatism denies the correspondence of beliefs to reality but affirms the truth that sustains human existence. One corollary of this understanding is that the search for true belief is closely related to the search for happiness (Rorty, 1999, p. 267). We are “clever animals trying to increase our happiness by continually reinventing ourselves.” (Rorty, 1999, p. 276) If so, we can pragmatically – not foundationally or metaphysically – assert that liberal democracy is better for human happiness in this ongoing search (as it is already *experienced* way of life in the West) until someone comes up with a better idea or utopia (Rorty, 1999, pp. 270, 273).

¹² His reasons are as follows: (1) Without European social and economic standards of living, it is not rational to import European democratic governmental systems. (2) The end of the cold war, by itself, is not a sufficient reason to hope for the progress of democracy, as the “kleptocrats” of the time have started to use more and more sophisticated instruments to sustain their injustices. (3) A global utopia can only become true by establishing a world federation following the spirit of the United Nations. However, the increasing number of atomic nation-states makes this kind of government less likely (Rorty, 1999, pp. 273-274).

Therefore, there is still sufficient reason to hold hope for Rorty's global egalitarian utopia to be aimed at and made real by human agencies.

6. Conclusion

This paper's point of departure is the question of how we can read Rorty's emphasis on social hope in the absence of any essentialist claim. While he asserts that hope does not need a *foundational* justification, I have offered to read him in a way that reveals his own *pragmatist* justifications.

Following his line of thinking led us to a conclusion consisting of three steps: Firstly, Rorty wants to eliminate the false hopes of Platonism (metaphysics) that seeks to arrive atemporal or ahistorical truths. It is nothing but a disappointment that this kind of philosophical inquiry brings to human beings. Therefore, not only is the absence of Platonist vocabulary does not cause for hopelessness, but we are better off without this vain Platonist hope.

Secondly, his notion of social hope, explained by the broader sense of solidarity, seems to function only in societies already sensitive to humiliation. In other words, there must be a minimal level of liberal freedoms to allow more. Even if it is the result of historical contingencies, cultural evolution allowed Western communities to cooperate with these practices. If it happened once in history, liberals could develop it further.

Thirdly, Rorty does not stop at this point and talks about global egalitarian utopia. Although there are many reasons to abandon this hope in reality, he chooses not to go down that road. What he pragmatically defends is that there is no pre-written destruction one can find in human destiny, but it is the human agent who would make real what is aimed. Furthermore, if we all seek in life is happiness, then, there is still hope for the establishment of a liberal democratic egalitarian world government, which has been experienced to be the most effective means of promoting human happiness to date.

Declarations / Beyanlar

Ethical Committee / Etik Kurul: There is no study that would require the approval of the Ethical Committee in this article. Bu makalede Etik Kurul Onayı gerektiren bir çalışma bulunmamaktadır.

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Kaynakça

- Bernstein, R. J. (2003). Rorty's Inspirational Liberalism. In C. Guignon & D. R. Hiley (Eds.), *Richard Rorty* (pp. 124-138). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Erez, L. (2011). *Rorty on Dignity, Humiliation and the Boundaries of the Moral Community* (Unpublished master's thesis). Darwin College, University of Cambridge, Cambridge.
- Koopman, C. (2006). Pragmatism as a Philosophy of Hope: Emerson, James, Dewey, Rorty. *The Journal of Speculative Philosophy* 20 (2), 106-116.
- Malachowski, A. (2002). *Richard Rorty*. New York: Routledge.
- Martin, A. M. (2014). *How We Hope: A Moral Psychology*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Meirav, A. (2009). The Nature of Hope. *Ratio* 22 (2), 216-33.
- Milona, M. (2018). Finding Hope. *Canadian Journal of Philosophy* 49 (5), 1-20.
- Rorty, R. (1982). *Consequences of Pragmatism*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press.
- _____. (1989). *Contingency, Irony, Solidarity*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- _____. (1994). After Philosophy, Democracy: Richard Rorty. In G. Borradori, (Ed.), R. Crocitto (trans.), *The American Philosopher: Conversations with Quine, Davidson, Putnam, Nozick, Danto, Rorty, Cavell, MacIntyre, and Kuhn* (pp. 103-117). Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- _____. (1998). *Truth and Progress*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- _____. (1999). *Philosophy and Social Hope*. New York: Penguin Books.
- _____. (2002). Hope and the Future. *Peace Review: A Journal of Social Justice* 14 (2), 149-155.
- Rorty R., Nystrom D., Puckett K. (2002). *Against Bosses, Against Oligarchies: A Conversation with Richard Rorty*. Chicago: Prickly Paradigm Press.
- Smith, N. H. (2005). Rorty on Religion and Hope. *Inquiry: An Interdisciplinary Journal of Philosophy* 48 (1), 76-98.
- _____. (2010). From the Concept of Hope to the Principle of Hope. In J. Horrigan & E. Wiltse (Eds.), *Hope Against Hope: Philosophies, Cultures and Politics of Possibility and Doubt* (pp. 1-22). Amsterdam: Rodopi.
- Stahl, T. (2020). Political Hope and Cooperative Community. In C. Blöser & T. Stahl (Eds.), *The Moral Psychology of Hope* (pp. 265-284). London; New York: Rowman and Littlefield.